

Thermodynamics for the Formation of Maleanilic Acids Complexes of Lanthanide(III) Ions

C. L. SHARMA*, R. S. ARYA, H. O. GUPTA and S. S. NARVI

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667

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The thermodynamic stepwise stability constants, free energy and the enthalpy and entropy changes for the formation of the complexes of lanthanide(III) ions with maleanilic, *p*-chloro maleanilic, *p*-bromo maleanilic, *p*-nitro maleanilic and *p*-methoxy maleanilic acids were determined. The values of $\log K_1$ increase regularly except for gadolinium. Analysis of the thermodynamic data indicates chelation of maleanilic acids through nitrogen of secondary amide and carboxylate groups.

THE significant studies on the thermodynamics, reported in the literature, are on the transition metal ion complexes of amino acids because of their biological interest¹⁻⁸. Such studies have also been made on the chelates of polyamino acids of lanthanide(III) ions⁹⁻¹³. No reference is available on the thermodynamics of the complexes of anilic acids containing a carboxylic and nitrogen of secondary amide group. The present communication deals with the determination of thermodynamic stability constants, ΔF , ΔH and ΔS , for the interaction of lanthanides with maleanilic acid and some of its derivatives. These complexes may also be of biological importance as the anilic acids and amino acids have the same coordinating sites.

Experimental

Rare earth oxides (A.R., B.D.H.) were dissolved in perchloric acid, evaporated to dryness and their solutions were then prepared in the solvent (20% v/v, methanol-water mixture). Maleanilic acid and its chloro, bromo, nitro and methoxy derivatives (*para* substituted) were prepared in the laboratory by the method of Rao and Ratnam¹⁴ and were recrystallised from alcohol. The formula of the derivatives is given below.

[X = Cl, Br, NO₂, OCH₃]

Carbon dioxide free potassium hydroxide was used for *pH* titrations. The experimental set up and methods used were the same as described earlier^{15,16}.

The thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes were determined potentiometrically following the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{17,18} as

adapted by Irving and Rossotti¹⁹ and employing the correction factors introduced by Van Uitert²⁰. The enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes were calculated from the temperature coefficient of the equilibrium constant in a medium of 0.1M NaClO₄. The calculations were made on DEC-2050 digital computer.

The accuracy of the *pK* values of acids and $\log K$ values of the complexes is ± 0.02 and ± 0.04 log units, respectively. Therefore the precisions of ΔH and ΔS are ± 0.56 k cal mole⁻¹ and $\pm .4$ cal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The values of dissociation constants *pK*₁ and *pK*₂ corresponding to the deprotonation of -COOH and -NH-, respectively at 22, 30 and 40° at ionic strength 0.1M NaClO₄ are given in Table 1. Table 2 summarises the values of the formation

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF ANILIC ACIDS IN 0.1 M NaClO₄ AT 22, 30 AND 40°

Acid	Temp. °C	<i>pK</i> ₁	<i>pK</i> ₂
MA	22	4.20	11.95
	30	4.13	11.55
	40	4.08	11.45
<i>p</i> -Chloro MA	22	4.15	11.82
	30	3.90	11.37
	40	3.83	11.16
<i>p</i> -Bromo MA	22	4.19	11.94
	30	3.95	11.40
	40	3.88	11.18
<i>p</i> -Nitro MA	23	3.92	11.25
	30	3.53	11.08
	40	3.44	10.90
<i>p</i> -Methoxy MA	22	4.15	12.00
	30	4.08	11.82
	40	4.03	11.78

MA = Maleanilic acid.

*Author for correspondence ; address : Vikas Nagar, 134/3, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF ANILIC ACIDS AT 22, 30 AND 40°

Acids	Temp. °C	Formation constants	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Eu ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Tb ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Ho ³⁺
MA	22	log K ₁	7.75	8.01	8.09	8.56	8.81	8.66	8.90	9.23	9.48
		log K ₂	7.33	7.84	7.88	8.14	8.38	8.28	8.42	8.56	8.61
		log K ₃	6.95	7.56	7.65	7.96	8.17	8.02	8.23	8.29	8.35
		log β ₃	22.03	23.41	23.62	24.66	25.36	24.96	25.55	26.08	26.44
	30	log K ₁	7.60	7.85	7.93	8.40	8.65	8.50	8.73	9.05	9.29
		log K ₂	7.25	7.75	7.80	8.05	8.30	8.20	8.33	8.46	8.50
		log K ₃	6.90	7.50	7.58	7.90	8.10	7.95	8.15	8.20	8.25
		log β ₃	21.75	23.10	23.31	24.35	25.05	24.65	25.21	25.71	26.04
	40	log K ₁	7.44	7.69	7.76	8.22	8.47	8.34	8.55	8.86	9.09
		log K ₂	7.16	7.66	7.71	7.95	8.20	8.12	8.23	8.35	8.38
		log K ₃	6.84	7.43	7.51	7.82	8.01	7.88	8.07	8.10	8.14
		log β ₃	21.44	22.78	22.98	23.99	24.68	24.34	24.85	25.31	25.61
<i>p</i> -Chloro-MA	22	log K ₁	8.50	8.80	8.91	9.06	9.32	9.17	9.49	9.66	9.77
		log K ₂	7.32	7.78	7.88	8.03	8.20	8.09	8.46	8.72	8.98
		log K ₃	7.21	7.36	7.61	7.77	7.93	7.83	8.09	8.45	8.71
		log β ₃	23.03	23.94	24.40	24.86	25.45	25.09	26.04	26.83	27.46
	30	log K ₁	8.35	8.65	8.75	8.90	9.15	9.00	9.30	9.45	9.55
		log K ₂	7.25	7.70	7.80	7.95	8.10	8.00	8.35	8.60	8.85
		log K ₃	7.15	7.30	7.55	7.70	7.85	7.75	8.10	8.35	8.60
		log β ₃	22.75	23.65	24.10	24.55	25.10	24.75	25.75	26.40	27.00
	40	log K ₁	8.19	8.49	8.58	8.73	8.96	8.83	9.30	9.23	9.33
		log K ₂	7.17	7.61	7.71	7.85	8.01	7.90	8.35	8.47	8.71
		log K ₃	7.08	7.24	7.48	7.62	7.76	7.67	8.10	8.24	8.48
		log β ₃	22.44	23.34	23.77	24.20	24.73	24.40	25.75	25.94	26.52
<i>p</i> -Bromo-MA	22	log K ₁	7.90	8.11	8.21	8.51	8.68	8.55	9.00	9.35	9.57
		log K ₂	7.50	7.90	8.06	8.37	8.38	8.38	8.46	8.63	8.93
		log K ₃	7.11	7.76	7.88	8.13	8.21	8.18	8.27	8.42	8.64
		log β ₃	22.51	23.77	24.15	25.01	25.27	25.01	25.73	26.40	27.14
	30	log K ₁	7.75	7.95	8.05	8.34	8.50	8.37	8.81	9.15	9.36
		log K ₂	7.40	7.80	7.95	8.26	8.26	8.29	8.36	8.51	8.79
		log K ₃	7.05	7.70	7.81	8.05	8.12	8.10	8.18	8.32	8.53
		log β ₃	22.20	23.45	23.81	24.65	24.88	24.76	25.35	25.98	26.68
	40	log K ₁	7.59	7.79	7.88	8.16	8.31	8.19	8.61	8.94	9.14
		log K ₂	7.29	7.69	7.84	8.14	8.13	8.18	8.25	8.37	8.64
		log K ₃	6.99	7.63	7.73	7.96	8.03	8.10	8.08	8.21	8.41
		log β ₃	21.87	23.11	23.45	24.26	24.47	24.47	24.94	25.52	26.19
<i>p</i> -Nitro-MA	22	log K ₁	8.11	8.26	8.42	8.62	8.76	8.70	8.92	9.69	9.76
		log K ₂	7.59	7.82	7.90	7.97	8.06	8.00	8.17	8.90	9.07
		log K ₃	6.97	7.27	7.30	7.50	7.68	7.58	7.75	8.56	8.77
		log β ₃	22.67	23.35	23.62	24.09	24.50	24.28	24.84	27.15	27.60
	30	log K ₁	7.95	8.10	8.25	8.45	8.60	8.55	8.75	9.50	9.56
		log K ₂	7.50	7.70	7.80	7.87	7.95	7.90	8.05	8.75	8.90
		log K ₃	6.90	7.20	7.22	7.42	7.60	7.50	7.65	8.45	8.65
		log β ₃	22.35	23.00	23.27	23.74	24.15	23.95	24.45	26.70	27.11
	40	log K ₁	7.79	7.93	8.07	8.27	8.43	8.39	8.58	9.30	9.35
		log K ₂	7.41	7.59	7.70	7.75	7.83	7.78	7.92	8.61	8.74
		log K ₃	6.83	7.12	7.13	7.33	7.50	7.40	7.54	8.33	8.53
		log β ₃	22.03	22.64	22.90	23.35	23.76	23.55	24.04	26.24	26.62
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-MA	22	log K ₁	8.55	8.80	8.90	8.96	9.12	9.06	9.18	10.00	10.16
		log K ₂	8.05	8.29	8.50	8.60	8.76	8.76	8.86	9.32	9.44
		log K ₃	7.60	8.11	8.31	8.40	8.58	8.49	8.70	8.89	9.07
		log β ₃	24.20	25.20	25.71	25.96	26.46	26.31	26.74	28.21	28.67
	30	log K ₁	8.40	8.65	8.75	8.80	8.95	8.90	9.00	9.80	9.95
		log K ₂	7.97	8.20	8.40	8.50	8.65	8.65	8.75	9.20	9.30
		log K ₃	7.55	8.05	8.25	8.34	8.50	8.42	8.61	8.78	8.95
		log β ₃	23.92	24.90	25.40	25.64	26.10	25.97	26.36	27.78	28.20
	40	log K ₁	8.25	8.49	8.58	8.63	8.77	8.74	8.81	9.58	9.73
		log K ₂	7.98	8.10	8.30	8.39	8.53	8.54	8.62	9.06	9.15
		log K ₃	7.49	7.98	8.17	8.25	8.41	8.34	8.50	8.66	8.82
		log β ₃	23.72	24.57	25.05	25.27	25.71	25.62	25.93	27.30	27.70

TABLE 3—STEPWISE ΔF° AND ΔH° VALUES (IN K CAL MOLE⁻¹) AND ΔS° VALUES IN GIBB'S MOLE⁻¹ (CAL MOLE⁻¹ DEG⁻¹) AT 22°

Acids	Thermodynamic parameters	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Eu ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Tb ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Ho ³⁺
MA	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	10.46	10.81	10.92	11.56	11.89	11.69	12.01	12.46	12.79
	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	9.90	10.58	10.64	10.99	11.31	11.18	11.37	11.56	11.62
	$-\Delta F_3^\circ$	9.38	10.21	10.33	10.48	11.03	10.83	11.11	11.19	11.27
	$-\Delta H_1$	6.97	7.15	7.41	7.85	7.98	7.18	8.06	8.28	8.72
	$-\Delta H_2$	3.92	4.03	4.12	4.36	4.50	3.70	4.55	4.79	5.02
	$-\Delta H_3$	2.61	3.05	3.25	3.49	3.92	3.25	3.70	4.36	4.68
	ΔS_1	11.78	12.31	11.85	12.54	13.23	15.18	13.33	13.79	13.43
	ΔS_2	20.23	22.18	24.98	22.44	23.13	25.31	23.10	22.90	22.34
	ΔS_3	22.97	24.26	23.96	24.62	24.12	25.64	25.08	23.13	22.31
<i>p</i> -Chloro-MA	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	11.47	11.88	12.03	12.23	12.58	12.38	12.81	13.04	13.19
	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	9.88	10.50	10.64	10.84	11.07	10.92	11.42	11.77	12.12
	$-\Delta F_3^\circ$	9.73	9.94	10.27	10.49	10.70	10.57	10.92	11.41	11.76
	$-\Delta H_1$	7.05	7.16	7.42	7.61	8.28	7.65	8.75	9.60	10.15
	$-\Delta H_2$	3.60	3.95	4.15	4.30	4.25	4.35	5.25	5.70	6.10
	$-\Delta H_3$	3.05	2.82	3.20	3.48	3.60	3.50	4.40	4.80	5.30
	ΔS_1	14.95	15.94	15.54	15.61	14.49	15.94	13.66	11.36	10.03
	ΔS_2	21.29	22.21	21.98	22.18	23.03	22.24	20.89	20.53	20.36
	ΔS_3	22.64	24.09	23.99	23.76	24.02	23.24	22.54	22.37	21.85
<i>p</i> -Bromo-MA	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	10.66	10.95	11.08	11.49	11.72	11.57	12.15	12.62	12.92
	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	10.12	10.66	10.88	11.30	11.31	11.31	11.42	11.65	12.05
	$-\Delta F_3^\circ$	9.60	10.48	10.64	10.97	11.08	11.04	11.16	11.37	11.66
	$-\Delta H_1$	7.05	7.20	7.40	7.95	8.45	8.05	8.92	9.20	9.80
	$-\Delta H_2$	4.80	4.85	5.00	5.30	5.70	4.80	4.95	6.00	6.70
	$-\Delta H_3$	2.65	3.05	3.50	3.95	4.20	4.30	4.35	4.82	5.25
	ΔS_1	12.21	12.61	12.41	11.91	11.02	11.72	10.89	11.52	10.30
	ΔS_2	18.02	19.67	19.87	20.30	18.98	22.08	21.91	19.14	18.12
	ΔS_3	23.53	25.18	24.19	23.79	23.30	22.87	23.73	22.18	21.71
<i>p</i> -Nitro-MA	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	10.95	11.15	11.37	11.64	11.83	11.74	12.04	13.08	13.18
	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	10.25	10.56	10.66	10.76	10.88	10.80	11.03	12.01	12.24
	$-\Delta F_3^\circ$	9.41	9.81	9.85	10.12	10.37	10.23	10.46	11.56	11.84
	$-\Delta H_1$	7.20	7.40	7.95	7.97	7.55	7.10	7.50	8.85	9.20
	$-\Delta H_2$	4.25	5.05	4.60	5.10	5.30	5.15	5.75	6.30	7.20
	$-\Delta H_3$	3.20	3.48	3.92	3.95	4.30	4.10	4.20	5.35	5.45
	ΔS_1	12.61	12.64	11.52	12.38	14.42	15.68	15.30	14.26	13.40
	ΔS_2	20.30	18.58	20.53	19.17	18.88	19.14	17.85	19.24	16.96
	ΔS_3	21.02	21.45	20.10	20.92	20.59	20.79	21.15	21.02	21.58
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-MA	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	11.54	11.88	12.01	12.10	12.31	12.23	12.39	13.50	13.72
	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	10.87	11.19	11.47	11.61	11.83	11.83	11.96	12.58	12.74
	$-\Delta F_3^\circ$	10.26	10.95	11.22	11.34	11.58	11.46	11.74	12.00	12.24
	$-\Delta H_1$	6.75	6.97	7.30	7.40	7.95	7.20	8.20	9.58	9.70
	$-\Delta H_2$	3.92	4.36	4.60	4.80	5.25	5.02	5.50	6.10	6.55
	$-\Delta H_3$	2.62	3.05	3.20	3.60	3.95	3.70	4.55	5.20	5.67
	ΔS_1	16.14	16.57	15.94	15.84	14.72	16.96	14.12	13.23	13.53
	ΔS_2	23.53	23.13	23.27	23.07	22.24	23.00	21.88	21.98	20.92
	ΔS_3	25.90	26.76	27.19	26.27	25.87	26.30	24.39	23.00	22.24

constants. The values of ΔF , ΔH and ΔS corresponding to the first, second and third step reactions are given in Table 3. The order of pK_a values is *p*-methoxy MA > MA > *p*-bromo MA $\approx$ *p*-chloro MA > *p*-nitro MA (MA = maleanilic acid). Thus the liberation of proton from -NH- is affected by both inductive and mesomeric effects of the substituents. Hence -NO₂, -Cl, or -Br substitution reduces the electron density at the reaction centre and causes the liberation of proton with great ease.

The reverse is true in the methoxy derivative. Comparatively smaller values of pK_a in the case of chloro, bromo and nitro derivatives may also be due to inductive effect the magnitude of which will be very small. As the carboxylate group is very far from the substituted phenyl group, pK_a value of methoxy derivative could not be explained on this basis. There is a regular increase in the values of $\log K_a$ from lanthanum to holmium except gadolinium. Such behaviour is also found

in other systems^{21,22}. This deviation in the values of $\log K_n$ and β_n of Gd(III) complexes may be due to the combined effect of ligand field stabilisation energy and the hydration number of the metal ion.

The rare earth metal ions generally coordinate predominantly to oxygen donors and weakly to nitrogen. The entropy values for the formation of these complexes are quite large and can not result from the change in coordination requirements. Hence, there must be contributions from both translational and configurational changes. These higher values may also be due to the negative charge on the coordinating sites which bring about a shielding of central tripositive ion from exercising its orienting influence on the unfrozen distant water dipoles. The decrease in entropy change for the second and third step reaction may be attributed to statistical effects which are also reflected in the values of ΔF and $\log K$ (stepwise) values. The trend obtained in the data of formation constants is also observed in ΔS and ΔH values and it appears that the stability of the complexes is mainly due to ΔS values which are large and positive.

The contribution to the total change in enthalpy by the carboxylate groups is generally very small and sometimes endothermic as in metal carboxylate complexes involving malonate, succinate, etc. The exothermic values given in each case are fairly high and can not be accounted for by metal carboxylate bond only. This also indicates the involvement of nitrogen in coordination.

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